

DURABILITY OF THE COMPOSITE/CONCRETE ADHESIVE BOND UNDER ACCELERATED AGEING

K. Benzarti¹, S. Chataigner², M. Quiertant¹ and C. Aubagnac²

¹ Université Paris Est, Laboratoire Central des Ponts et Chaussées (LCPC)
58 bld Lefebvre, 75732, Paris Cedex 15, France
benzarti@lcpc.fr

² Laboratoire Régional d'Autun, Autun, France

SUMMARY

The durability of concrete specimens strengthened by bonded composite materials has been investigated. Time evolution of the concrete/composite adhesive bond strength was studied under controlled ageing conditions, by using different mechanical tests. Structural evolutions of the polymer adhesive during ageing were also studied by DSC analyses and mechanical tests.

Keywords: Concrete infrastructures, composite reinforcements, adhesive bond, durability, hydrothermal ageing

1. INTRODUCTION

Composite materials are commonly used worldwide for the strengthening and repair of civil structures. In France, such methods are increasingly applied to the rehabilitation or upgrading of damaged infrastructures [1]. If the efficiency of the carbon reinforced polymer (CFRP) strengthening techniques has been clearly demonstrated, the durability of the adhesive bond at the concrete/composite interface is still a matter of investigation. Several authors have reported substantial decreases in the adhesive bond strength of FRP strengthened concrete specimens submitted to accelerated ageing conditions, such as freeze-thaw /dry-heat cycles, immersion in salt solutions or exposure to humid environments [2-6]. Saturated humidity is often found to be one of the most detrimental factors to the adhesive bond properties [5].

In this study, concrete specimens reinforced either by carbon fibre sheets (*i.e.*, CFS implemented according to the wet lay-up process) or by pultruded CFRP plates were submitted to accelerated ageing conditions in humid air (40°C and 95% R.H.). The evolution of the adhesive strength was then monitored as a function of ageing time, using either pull-off or shear loading tests. Simultaneously, the microstructural evolutions of the polymer adhesive due to hydrothermal ageing were investigated by DSC analyses (differential scanning calorimetry) and by tensile loading tests.

On the basis of these results, the effects of accelerated ageing on the properties of the concrete/composite adhesive bond are highlighted. The influence of several parameters are discussed, such as the nature of the FRP system (CFS or CFRP plates), the surface preparation of concrete, the presence of a carbonated layer at the concrete surface, or the test configuration used for the adhesive bond strength assessment.

2. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

2.1. Investigation on concrete/composites interfaces using pull-off characterizations

In a first set of experiments, reinforced concrete slabs were prepared as follows: concrete slabs (dimensions 30x30x5 cm³) were cast from CEM I Portland cement and silico-calcareous aggregates, with a water-to-cement ratio of 0.5. The final material exhibited a compressive strength of 35 MPa. These concrete slabs were then divided into 2 series with 2 different surface preparations: either sand-blasting or grinding. Some of these slabs were also subjected to a carbonation process for 1 month under CO₂ at 20°C and 65% RH, in order to obtain a carbonated surface layer of 10 mm.

Specimens of each series were then strengthened by 2 types of commercially available FRP systems: half were reinforced using the wet lay-up process based on carbon fiber sheet (CFS), and the remaining half by bonded CFRP plates (Figs. 1a and 1b, respectively). Polymer adhesives were bi-component epoxy systems from the market. Implementation was achieved by experienced staff from FRP supplier companies.

Finally, 8 types of model concrete/composite interfaces were obtained:

- sand-blasted concrete + CFS,
- sand-blasted concrete + CFRP plates,
- grinded concrete + CFS,
- grinded concrete + CFRP plates,
- sand-blasted/carbonated concrete + CFS
- sand-blasted/carbonated concrete + CFRP
- grinded/carbonated concrete + CFS
- grinded/carbonated concrete + CFRP

All strengthened slabs were exposed to saturated humidity at 40°C in a climatic chamber. After increasing ageing periods, adhesive bond characterizations were carried-out by pull-off tests using an Elcometer adhesion tester (Fig. 1c), according to ASTM D4541 standard [7].

Figure 1. Concrete slabs strengthened either by bonded carbon fiber sheets (a) or pultruded CFRP plates (b), and pull-off test device for the bond strength assessment (c).

Time evolutions of the adhesive bond strengths are depicted in Figures 2a to 2d for the 8 model concrete/composite interfaces. The last data were collected after an ageing period of 20 months (628 days). Mean values are calculated as the average of 6 test results, and their standard deviations are also indicated on the figures.

Table 1 makes it possible to compare the values of the pull-off strength in the initial state and after 628 days ageing, and reports the corresponding variations for the 8 model bonded interfaces.

Figure 2. Pull-off strength *versus* ageing time for the 8 model concrete/composite interfaces. Mean values are averages of 6 test results.

Table 1. Values of the pull-off strength in the initial state and after an ageing period of 628 days, and corresponding variations for the 8 model bonded interfaces.

Type of bonded interface	Initial strength (MPa)	Strength after 628 days ageing (MPa)	Variation (%)
<i>Sand-blasted concrete + CFS</i>	3.3	1.8	- 46
<i>Grinded concrete + CFS</i>	2.7	1.4	- 48
<i>Sand-blasted concrete + CFRP</i>	3.0	1.6	- 49
<i>Grinded concrete + CFRP</i>	2.5	1.0	- 58
<i>Sand blasted/carbonated concrete + CFS</i>	3.8	3.1	- 18
<i>Grinded/carbonated concrete + CFS</i>	3.7	2.9	- 21
<i>Sand blasted/carbonated concrete + CFRP</i>	3.7	3.8	+ 3
<i>Grinded/carbonated concrete + CFRP</i>	3.6	3.2	- 11

A large dispersion is observed for the strength values, which is a general feature of the pull-off test. However, several trends can be drawn from these experiments since they were observed throughout the test campaign.

A focus on strengthened specimens prepared from non carbonated concrete surfaces (Figs. 2a and 2b), leads to the following remarks:

- the surface preparation of concrete has a slight effect on the strength level of the bonded interface : sand-blasted concrete surfaces lead globally to higher bond strength values than grinded ones, probably due to a higher cohesion of the superficial concrete layer. Moreover, the aspect of the fractured surfaces is usually smoother for specimens based on grinded concrete slabs,
- accelerated ageing induces a progressive and **significant decrease in the adhesive bond strength**, especially for grinded concrete slabs strengthened by CFRP plates. Indeed the latter specimens exhibit a drop of properties of 58% after an ageing period of 628 days, whereas the other specimens are “limited” to a decrease of 46 to 49%, (Table 1). This result suggests that concrete-CFRP interfaces might be more sensitive to humid environments than concrete-CFS interfaces,
- whereas the failure mode is initially cohesive within the concrete substrate, an increasing number of mixed or adhesive failures is observed over ageing time, as shown by Figure 3. This is also consistent with a substantial degradation of the adhesive bond or to a decrease in the epoxy joint properties due to humid ageing.

Figure 3. Examples of mixed failure mode observed for model concrete/composites interfaces subjected to humid ageing (characterization by pull-off test).

When considering strengthened specimens prepared from carbonated concrete slabs (Figs. 2c and 2d, and Table 1), it is found that:

- values of the pull-off strength are globally higher than those of specimens prepared from non carbonated slabs, both in the initial and aged states. Indeed, by decreasing the porosity of the superficial concrete layer, the carbonation treatment has significantly improved the mechanical properties of the substrate,
- as carbonation took place after the sand-blasting or grinding treatments, the influence of those surface treatments is not clearly discernable here,
- a major feature is that the decrease of the bond strength during humid ageing is much more limited (-11 to -21%) than for specimens based on non carbonated substrates. And even, no significant variation is observed for the “*sand blasted/carbonated concrete + CFRP*” interface. This result suggests that the main degradation process involves moisture diffusion from the concrete surface

towards the bonded interface and the adhesive joint. The diffusion kinetics might be much slower in the case of carbonated concrete substrates, since the porosity is reduced within the 10 mm thick carbonated layer.

2.2. Investigation on strengthened concrete blocs using both pull-off and shear loading characterizations.

In a second set of experiments, it is proposed to carry-out further investigations using two characterization methods instead of one in order to provide comparative data, *i.e.*, pull-off and shear loading tests.

For these experiments, two types of specimens were used: concrete blocs strengthened by pultruded CFRP plates or by carbon fiber sheets (CFS) from the market. The main objective was to compare more precisely the ageing behavior of the 2 types of strengthening systems.

Test specimens were prepared as follows:

- concrete blocs of dimensions $21 \times 21 \times 41 \text{ cm}^3$ were cast from CEM II 32.5 cement and silico-calcareous aggregates, with a water-to-cement ratio of 0.55. The compressive strength of the resulting material was around 37 MPa,
- for half of these concrete blocs, a sand-blasting treatment was made on the upper side and 2 pieces of CFRP plates were bonded with a commercial epoxy adhesive (noted epoxy A). One zone is intended for the shear test (bonded length of 250 mm) and the other for the pull-off tests, as shown in Figure 4.
- for the other half, a grinding treatment was achieved on the upper surface, and 2 strips of CFS were bonded in a similar way, using a second epoxy adhesive (noted epoxy B),
- test zones devoted to the shear loading characterizations were instrumented by 5 strain gages, according to the configuration depicted in Figure 5. The objective was to monitor the deformations of the composite materials along the bonded interface during the shear tests and to evaluate the anchorage length.

Figure 4. Principle of the shear loading test and picture of the home-made device. One can notice the test zone for the pull-off characterizations on the front side of the sample. Further details of the shear-test device are available in reference [8].

Figure 5. Locations of the 5 strain gages along bonded interface (15, 50, 90, 135 and 200 mm from the border of the adhesive joint).

In addition, samples of pure epoxy adhesives A and B were casted and cured at room temperature. Such specimens were intended for DSC and tension loading tests, in order to assess the evolutions of the adhesive properties induced by humid ageing.

All test specimens (strengthened concrete slabs and samples of epoxy adhesives) were then exposed to saturated humidity at 40°C in a climatic chamber. Then next sections will focus respectively on the ageing behaviors of the bulk polymer adhesives, the concrete-CFRP interface, and finally the concrete-CFS interface.

2.2.1. Ageing behaviour of the bulk epoxy adhesives

Figure 6 depicts the evolutions of the glass transition temperature of the bulk epoxies A and B during ageing at 40°C and 95% RH, as determined by DSC analyses using a heating rate of 1.5 °C.min⁻¹. These evolutions reflect the competition between 2 antagonistic mechanisms: the ongoing cross-linking process at 40°C and the plasticization effect due to the diffusion of moisture into the polymer network:

- both adhesives exhibit an initial increase in T_g due to the cross-linking process,
- for epoxy A, the plasticization effect becomes rapidly predominant and a sharp drop of T_g is observed after few hours. Then, as the moisture sorption kinetics slows down, the cross-linking process leads to another increase in T_g,
- for epoxy B, T_g reaches a plateau value around 64°C.

Figure 6. Evolutions of the glass transition temperatures T_g for epoxies A and B (DSC analyses with a heating rate of 1.5 °C.min⁻¹).

Figure 7 shows the stress-strain curves for epoxies A and B submitted to tensile loadings, both in the initial state and after various ageing periods:

- initially, the 2 adhesives exhibit an elastic behavior but mechanical properties of epoxy B are better than those of epoxy A (higher strength and strain at failure),
- during ageing, both mechanical behaviors evolve and become elasto-plastic, which is consistent with the plasticization effect revealed by DSC. After an ageing period of 7 months, the tensile strength is decreased by a factor 5 for epoxy A and 2 for epoxy B. For aged specimens A, one can notice that the value of the tensile strength becomes very close to that of the concrete.

Figure 7. tensile loading tests for bulk epoxies A (a) and B (b). Stress-strain curves are presented for initial samples and aged specimens.

2.2.2. Ageing behaviour of the concrete-CFRP interface

Concrete blocs strengthened by CFRP plates and based on epoxy adhesive A were then characterized by pull-off tests and shear loading tests, after various ageing periods. Results are respectively presented in Figures 8 and 9:

- for both test methods, it is found that humid ageing induces a progressive evolution of the failure mode from a concrete failure towards a cohesive failure in the epoxy joint. Such a phenomenon can be correlated to the large decrease in the mechanical properties of aged epoxy A, as shown in the previous section,
- in the case of pull-off tests, a decrease in strength is also observed in agreement with the evolution of the failure mode,
- however, for the shear tests, no significant evolution of the maximum shear load could be found, which seems contradictory with the observed change in failure mode.

In order to clear up this issue, the signals provided by the strain gages during the shear tests were examined. Figure 10 shows the strain profiles of the CFRP plate along the bonded interface, at various load levels. Diagrams are plotted both for the initial and aged specimens (ageing period of 12 months).

(b) Initial state (concrete failure)

(c) Aged specimen (joint failure)

Figure 8. Pull-off results for CFRP strengthened blocs: pull-off strength *versus* Ageing time (a) and pictures of fractured surfaces in the initial (b) and aged (c) states.

(b) Initial state (concrete failure)

(c) Aged specimen (joint failure)

Figure 9. Shear test results for CFRP strengthened blocs: Maximum shear load *versus* Ageing time (a) and pictures of fractured surfaces for initial (b) and aged (c) specimens.

Figure 10. Strain profiles of the composite along the bonded interface at various load levels during the shear test, for initial (a) and aged (b) CFRP strengthened specimens.

For the initial specimen, the strain profile reveals the existence of an anchorage length with a value around 130 mm (Fig. 10a). It is found that humid ageing strongly affects the strain distribution along the bonded interface and leads to a significant increase in the anchorage length (Fig. 10b). This phenomenon is a probable consequence of the low mechanical properties and large plasticization of epoxy A after ageing.

In that case, the fact that the maximum shear load is little affected by humid ageing might result from a change in the shear load transfer mechanism along the interface. Further work based on a finite element modeling is needed to validate this hypothesis.

2.2.3. Ageing behaviour of the concrete-CFS interface

Finally, concrete blocs strengthened by CFS and based on epoxy adhesive B were characterized by pull-off tests and shear loading tests, after various ageing periods. Results are respectively presented in Figures 11 and 12 :

- in that case, pull-off experiments do not reveal any significant change in the pull-off strength (Fig. 11a) nor any evolution of the failure mode, which always remains a concrete failure (Fig. 11b and 11c),
- with regard to the shear experiments, it can be noticed that the maximum shear load remains also constant (Fig. 12a). However, an evolution of the failure mode is observed from a concrete failure towards an interfacial failure, which is consistent with a substantial degradation of the adhesive bond during ageing (Fig. 12b and 12c). The fact that the maximum shear load is not affected despite the change in the adhesive bond properties might result again from a modification of the shear load transfer along the interface and from an increase in the anchorage length, as shown on Figure 13. Nevertheless, the ageing mechanism seems to be more complex than in the previous case of CRFP strengthened blocs, since it might not only involve plasticization of the epoxy polymer but also degradation of the interfacial bond.

Another important finding is that the pull-off test may be less sensitive than the shear test, since no evolution of the failure mode is detected after ageing with the first method. It is believed that variations in the pull-off results (strength and failure mode)

are only observed for very large changes in the joint properties, which was the case for epoxy A in the previous section.

(b) Initial state (concrete failure)

(c) Initial state (concrete failure)

Figure 11. Pull-off results for CFS strengthened blocs: pull-off strength *versus* Ageing time (a) and pictures of fractured surfaces for initial (b) and aged (c) specimens.

(b) Initial state (concrete failure)

(c) Aged state (mixed/interfacial failure)

Figure 12. Shear test results for CFS strengthened blocs: Maximum shear load *versus* Ageing time (a) and pictures of fractured surfaces for initial (b) and aged (c) specimens.

Figure 13. Strain profiles of the composite along the bonded interface at various load levels during the shear test, for initial (a) and aged (b) CFS strengthened specimens.

3. CONCLUSIONS

In the first part of this study, the ageing behavior of model concrete-composite interfaces was investigated and the influence of several parameters was evaluated using pull-off characterizations. It was found that:

- humid ageing causes a progressive and significant decrease in the pull-off strength of the bonded interfaces for CFS and CFRP strengthened specimens prepared from non carbonated concrete slabs. Moreover, the failure mode evolves from a substrate failure towards a mixed or interfacial failure,
- the surface treatment of the concrete slabs has a slight effect on mechanical tests, since higher pull-off strengths are globally obtained with sand-blasting compared to grinding,
- for strengthened specimens prepared from carbonated concrete slabs, the pull-off properties were only little affected by humid ageing. This result suggests that the main degradation process involves moisture diffusion from the concrete surface towards the adhesively bonded joint.

In the second part, the ageing behavior of CFS and CFRP strengthened concrete blocs was assessed using both pull-off and shear loading characterizations.

- the epoxy adhesives used for the bonding exhibited a decrease in mechanical strength during humid ageing, as well as a pronounced elasto-plastic behavior. An extensive plasticization of the polymer network (decrease of T_g) was also observed for the adhesive A used for the bonding of CFRP materials,
- the shear loading tests revealed an evolution of the failure mode, from a substrate failure towards a cohesive failure within the polymer joint in the case of CFRP strengthened specimens, and towards an interfacial failure in the case of CFS reinforced blocs. Therefore, it is proposed that the ageing mechanism is

mainly based on polymer plasticization in the first case, and both on plasticization and bond degradation in the latter case.

Despite these changes in the failure mode, no evolution of the maximum shear loads was observed during ageing regardless the type of specimen considered. Indeed, signals provided by strain gages showed that the decrease in the joint properties was counterbalanced by a redistribution of the load transfer along the bonded interface, and by an increase in the anchorage length.

- finally, results of the pull-off characterizations were consistent with those of the shear tests in the case of CFRP reinforced blocs (change in the failure mode), but not in the case of CFS strengthened specimens (no change at all). It is believed that the pull-off test has a lower sensitivity than the shear test to the evolution of the bond properties during ageing. Such evolutions are only detected when the tensile strength of the epoxy adhesive reach the same range than that of concrete.

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References

1. Luyckx J., 1999. Techniques de l’Ingénieur AM5620 : 1-10.
2. Karbhari V.M., Chin J.W. et al., 2003. Durability Gap Analysis for Fiber-Reinforced Polymer Composites in Civil Infrastructure, *Journal of Composites for Construction* 7(3) : 238-247
3. Gangarao H.V.S., Taly N., Vijay P.V., 2006. Reinforced concrete design with FRP composites, CRC Press
4. Karbhari V.M., 2007. Durability of composites for civil structural applications. Cambridge: Woodhead Publishing
5. Grace, N.F & Singh, S.B., 2005. Durability of Carbon Fiber-Reinforced Polymer Strengthened Concrete Beams, *ACI Structural Journal* 102(1): 40-51
6. Marouani S., Curtil L. & Hamelin P., 2008. Composites realized by hand lay-up process in a civil environment: initial properties and durability, *Materials & Structures* 41(5): 831-851
7. ASTM D4541, 2002. Standard test method for pull-off strength of coating using portable adhesion testers. American Society for Testing and Materials: 1-10.
8. Chataigner S., Caron J.F. et al., 2008. Characterization of composite-to-concrete interface: Use of the cohesive zone approach, Fourth International Conference on FRP Composites in Civil Engineering (CICE2008) 22-24July, Zurich, Switzerland, CD-Rom paper.